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Heat treatment to increase callus induction efficiency in anther culture of IR42

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Indica rices are generally regarded as recalcitrant varieties in anther culture because of their low, if ever, callus production and plant regeneration efficiencies. IR42 is one of the more important IR varieties because of its resistance to major insect pests and diseases and high yielding ability. One of the drawbacks to its popularity in farmers' fields, however, is its late maturity. It is important to get variants that not only retain IR42's agronomic characteristics but also are early maturing. Anther culture can be a potential tool for producing such variants but the problem of callus induction and plant regeneration efficiencies should first be solved. By applying heat treatment to rice panicles before culturing the anthers and manipulating media components, we were able to increase callus production in IR42.

Rice panicles with 5-10 cm distance between the auricle of the flag leaf and that of the subtending leaf were collected for the study. Each panicle was divided into the upper and bottom portions and a floret was collected from the middle section of each half for determination of the stage of pollen development. Only anthers with pollen grains between the mid-uninucleate to early binucleate stages of development were plated. The remaining spikelets of each portion were divided into 3 lots and placed separately in petri dishes containing 1.5% water agar. Each lot was subjected to 1 of the following heat treatments at 35 °C: 0, 5, and 15 min, followed by a cold treatment at 10 °C for 7 d. Anthers from all treatments were plated in two media which contain

Effect of heat treatment on callus induction efficiency in IR42 anther culture.

Treatment	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (no.)	% callus production
<i>E10 medium</i>			
H ₀	345	34	9.8
H ₅	623	76	12.2
H ₁₅	439	90	20.5
<i>ER medium</i>			
H ₀	565	64	11.3
H ₅	706	102	14.4
H ₁₅	577	84	14.6

the salts and vitamins of Gamborg's B5 medium but differ in growth regulators. E10 contained 0.5 g benzyladenine/liter, 0.5 mg indole acetic acid/liter, and 1 mg 2,4-D/liter while ER had 0.11 mg zeatin/liter, 2 mg 2,4-D/liter, and 0.07 mg picloram/liter.

Heat treatment increased callus induction efficiency in both media (see table). At 0 and 5 min, ER induced higher efficiencies than E10. At 15 min, however, there was a dramatic increase using E10 media. Cold shock, which has been a part of the standard operational procedure in anther culture in most cereals, promotes the synchrony and viability of the pollen grains and may activate some enzymes which are necessary in callus production. On the other hand; heat treatment has been popular in *Brassica* genus. This study demonstrates that heat treatment before cold shock could increase callus production in IR42. In the same manner as in cold shock, heat may, aside from promoting synchrony and viability, activate enzymes necessary to induce the pollen grains toward vegetative development (in this case, callus production) instead of their normal generative function.

Some of the calli produced have been transferred to plant regeneration medium to determine the plant regeneration efficiency after heat treatment. *S*